
SOIL STABILISATION OF CLAYEY SOIL BY USING COAL ASH AND STONE DUST

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INTRODUCTION

The current study explores the best coal ash similar to the fly ash dosage for enhancing the soil's overall unconfined compressive strength. The two types of fly ash used come from the Southeast Asian region, respectively, and are both produced when coal is burned in a generator that generates electricity. A mixture of organic clays exhibiting modest to significant flexibility and inorganic silts makes up the soil, which was extracted from the paddy fields in the selected sector. UCS studies on moulds composed of pure soil and soil mixed with fly ash were conducted during curing durations of three, seven, fourteen, twenty-eight, and ninety days, with an optimal moisture content of 19%–24%. Observations show that pure soil's highest possible dry density is 1.615 g/cm³, and its OMC is 20.30% (Sneha *et al.*, 2021). Fly ash and stone ash treatment results in an ultimate dry bulk density of 1.615 g/cm³ for the soil, which raises both OMC and MDD. When fly ash is applied, the soil's OMC and MDD increase. The increase in these two types of ash content allowed for identifying both the zone of activity and the degeneration zone of strength development.

Clay soils normally exhibit rigidity when dry but become pliable when saturated with water. Soft clays have high elastic modulus and low bearing capacity. This study used recycled waste stone effluent from slab stone manufacturing and stone washing activities to restore clayey soil with lime. Experiments were conducted in the lab to ascertain whether lime-mixed waste stone granules effectively stabilise very fine clayey soil (Lindhand Lemenkova, 2022). The soil samples were subjected to a variety of laboratory procedures, including unconfined compression tests, Atterberg limits tests, size distribution analyses, typical Proctor compaction tests, and Atterberg limits tests. The various soil types were used in combination with variable proportions of lime and powdered crushed waste stone.

The findings indicate that when more waste stone dust is added to lime, clayey soil becomes less elastic and exhibits variations in its maximum dry density & ideal moisture content. The tests performed for free compressive toughness plus California bearings revealed that the inclusion of wasted stones powder although substituted lime raised the scores of UCS as well as CBR by as much as 6% waste stones substance that 7% lime content, as well as 6% concealer content. This suggests that, in some construction applications, waste stone dust may be a suitable replacement for lime. To find the best ratios for various types of waste stones & building-related supplies, more investigation is necessary.

LITERATURE REVIEW

There has yet to be much discussion in the literature about the technical properties of metallic stabilisation materials that incorporate waste stone powder. Bilgin *et al.* (2012) looked at waste marble dust's appropriateness as a part of industrial brick. They agreed that putting stone dust as a coating increased the industrial brick's mechanical, chemical, and physical strength (Bilgin *et al.*, 2012).

Karakus (2011) examined stone mastic asphalt manufactured from Diyarbakir basalt rubble. Most SMA comprises 93–94% aggregate, 6–7% bitumen, and additives. According to test results, Karakus (2011) shows that basalt recyclables can be used as cementitious materials and aggregates in SMA and that their characteristics are within the desired range (Karakus, 2011).

Demirel (2010) looked into the effects of waste stone dusted shavings as fine sand in mortar on its existing properties. It was shown that the compressive strength might be enhanced by substituting WMD at particular ratios for the very small particles that would go through a 0.25 mm sieve. Environmental contamination has been greatly exacerbated by sodium silicate, a byproduct of limestone processing facilities. Consequently, by substituting it for fine aggregate in ordinary-strength concretes that include, it may be theoretically granted to reduce contamination,

especially in regions where marble manufacturing is overly abundant, plus to use fewer raw materials as a whole (Demirel, 2010).

PROBLEM STATEMENTS

Utilising materials like coal and cement raises the cost of construction. The use of recyclable materials in anchoring unstable soils has grown in acceptance since it promotes kinder-to-the-environment building practices, safeguards the environment, and reduces project costs. When clay soil is controlled by limestone dust, its strength qualities and plastic limit increase while its specific gravity and plasticity index decrease.

Lime and cement have been combined with industrial waste products such fly ash, slag, rice husk ash, sludge, & waste stone powder to enhance the geotechnical qualities of soils. Over the past 30 years, studies have been conducted on the stabilising effects of employing rice husk ash in soil development methods. Some research suggests that the ash from rice husks can improve soils originally consolidated with limestone or stone dust.

NEED FOR RESEARCH

The use of industrial trash in place of conventional additives to create new soil stabilisers has been documented in numerous research. Low-bearing clay was maintained during a study experiment using a blend of lime plus blast furnace slag. This substance increases the soil's strength and carrying capacity, especially during floods. Other research studies have examined pozzolanic contaminants with the value of rice husk ash, cement ash from kilns, and cement dust as effective stabilising agents, especially for clayey soils. Based on such, the need for research on these matters is more important.

OBJECTIVES

1. To research the optimal usage for coal ash.
2. To learn more about how the combination of coal ash and stone dust can increase soil's capacity to bear more weight.
3. To investigate the process of ingredients on soil permeability.
4. To examine the effects of coal ash and stone dust on the number of particles and OMC of clayey soil.
5. To investigate how adding lime and coal ash impacts soil CBR.
6. To investigate how the curing procedure affects the properties of clayey soil.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Soil stabilisation was first created in the USA in 1904 as an affordable and "environmentally friendly" technique (Mekonnen *et al.*, 2020). By incorporating stabilisers into the soil, the soil is chemically fixed to accomplish the primary objective of enhancing the geotechnical behaviour of the ground. This study was carried out in three stages so that the concrete strain, compaction properties, compressibility, and permeability of composite samples could be thoroughly and methodically investigated.

The data were then accurately evaluated using scanning electrons & optical microscopy to evaluate them from a microstructural perspective. While XRD was implemented to identify the aspects of the mineral and FTIR to detect differences in chemical composition, EDS was utilised to corroborate the chemical characterisation and elemental analysis (Martinset *et al.*, 2021). Applying these analytical methods allowed a thorough assessment of the material's properties and behaviour under varied conditions. These findings can help future studies and advances in the sector. The secondary research structure will follow the overall methodology in the general perspective of the prescribed topic.

SOURCE OF DATA

To clarify and illustrate the importance of employing soil stabilisations, data on the mandated specific topic of Soil Stabilisation by stone dust and verified utilisations of coal ash may be discovered in depth from verified internet

and university-based, governmental, and private sources. Engineers and construction experts can use these resources to make knowledgeable choices about the best techniques for stabilising soil in their projects.

SAMPLING

According to papers and articles, a relevant advertisement can aid in the subsequent expansion of a well-known restaurant. Data on similar practices utilised by other restaurants are gathered to improve customer levels. For the modern world to prosper, new consumers are required.

EXPECTED OUTCOME

To remain competitive in the market today and improve the customer level after a set period, other restaurants must monitor the data they collect in this way. The literature has lately undergone a thorough review to establish whether lime improves the geotechnical properties of stone dust soil. For this, various methods, different types of soil, coal ash levels, drying conditions, and soil types were used. The stone dust-treated soil's lime content and mineralogy both have an effect. Benefits include a markedly improved soil structural strength, decreased soil flexibility (increasing workability), and increased soil durability. Carbonation, sulphate attack, and the environment are examples of negative effects.

Given their limits, partly because of their chemical makeup, alternatives to coal can be suggested. A magnesium base was used in a few trials to strengthen the soil, greatly improving the soil's strength, ability to flow, and overall durability. Careful research is necessary to ascertain this chemical's effectiveness in stabilising soil. Other substances, like flying ash, coal ash, or stone dust, have additionally been employed for stabilising the soil with different degrees of success. One should consider all available options, expenses, and environmental implications to make the optimal choice.

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